

survival and shorter life span. GLH fed on xylem in all varieties tested. However, they also fed on phloem in Utri Merah, Utri Rajapan, and TN1.

Regardless of the number of GLH inoculated, Utri Merah, Utri Rajapan, and Gam Pai 30-12-15 had low seedling infection (see figure). Most seedlings of the test varieties, except TN1, were infected with RTBV alone (Table 2). However, a few seedlings of Gam Pai 30-12-15, Utri Rajapan, IR50, IR58, and IR60 were infected with both RTBV and RTSV.

Although most RTV-resistant varieties also have GLH resistance, Utri Rajapan and Utri Merah were GLH susceptible

Table 2. Presence of RTBV and RTSV in RTV-infected seedlings in the fire.

Variety	Plants tested ^a (no.)	Plants (no.) with viruses ^b		
		RTBV + RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
Gam Pai 30-12-15	30	2	25	0
ASD7	30	0	25	0
ASD8	30	0	23	0
Utri Merah	30	0	25	0
Utri Rajapan	25	1	22	0
IR50	30	1	24	0
IR58	30	4	24	0
IR60	30	5	24	0
TN1	30	18	2	0

^aThe test plants were inoculated plants with 1 or 3 or 5 insects per seedling. ^bPresence of viruses was detected 4 wk after inoculation.

despite strong RTV resistance. They can be a good source of RTV resistance

because their resistance may be stable and consistent. □

Reaction of rice varieties to sheath blight (ShB)

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ShB has become a serious rice disease in much of India. In 1982 and 1983 kharif we screened rices for ShB resistance under lowland and rainfed upland conditions. Seedlings were planted in two 2-m-long rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Each test variety was surrounded by highly susceptible Pankaj and Jaya. At tillering stage, the test plants were inoculated just above the water level with a pure culture of ShB. Reactions were recorded using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES).

IR8, IR42, IR32, Shangsamba, Tumai

Reaction to ShB of rice varieties under lowland and rainfed upland conditions, Wangbal, India.

Score ^a	Varieties	
	Lowland conditions	Rainfed upland conditions
0	IR8, IR42, IR46, IR32, KD-2-6-3 (Moirangphou/Lawagin), Acham, Shangsamba, Tumai Angouba, Milyang 58, Suweon 294	IR8, IR42, IR32, Shangsamba, Tumai Angouba, Milyang 58, Suweon 294
1	—	KD-2-6-3, IR46, Acham
3	US2, IR840-85, Milyang 54, Suweon 287, IR1561-228-3-1, RP9-4, RP-8-9, Punshi, Phou-oibi	—
5	IR1421-11, IR350, RPW-6-13, Tetep, Tadukan	—
7	IR54, IR34, IR43, CR238-27-40-28	Milyang 54, Suweon 287, IR840-85, Tetep, Tadukan, IR1421-11, IR34, IR43
9	Pankaj, Jaya	RP8-9, RP-9-4, US2, CR238-27-40-28, Punshi, Phou-oibi, Pankaj, Jaya, IR54, IR350, RPW6-13, IR1561-228-3-1

^aBy the 1980 SES.

Angouba, Milyang 58, and Suweon 294 had ShB resistance (see table). Varieties

were more susceptible to ShB under rainfed upland conditions. □

BG90-2 released in China

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The first formal rice germplasm exchange between the People's Republic of China and IRRI was in 1972. Since then many varieties and advanced lines from IRRI and other countries have been sent to China. One of those varieties and lines is BG90-2 from Sri Lanka. In 1983, BG90-2

Morphoagronomic characteristics of BG90-2 at different sites in China.

City, province	Plant ht (cm)	Growth duration (d)	Seeding to full heading (d)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains/panicle	Fertile grains/panicle	Sterility (%)	1,000-seed wt (g)
Nanjing, Jiangsu	113	154	115	26	161	128	20.3	26.6
Hangzhou, Zhejiang	104	136	105	29	234	134	42.8	25.9
Changsha, Hunan	96	131	107	28	140	105	25.0	25.8
Guangzhou, Guangdong	109	146	—	24	133	90	32.0	26.0

was grown on about 140,000 ha in Jiangsu Province and other provinces in the Nanjing region along the Yantze River. This area produces more than 50% of the

midseason rice grown in China.

BG90-2 has high, stable yield potential with normal fertilization, yielding 6.7 to 7.5 t/ha. It yields 10-15% and 7-10%

more than the local modern improved variety Nanjing 11 and hybrid Nanyou 6.

BG90-2 has high, stable BB resistance, and is a source of BB resistance in breed-

ing programs. It is one of 12 best resistant sources among 10,688 accessions screened by the Plant Protection Institute of the Guangdong Provincial Academy of

Agricultural Sciences. BG90-2 also has good morphoagronomic characters (see table). □

New sources of resistance to major rice diseases

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We evaluated 46 rice varieties at TNAU, Coimbatore, for reaction to brown spot (BS), bacterial blight (BB), and sheath rot (ShR) under artificial screening conditions using the Standard Evaluation

System for Rice. AS18699 and AS19703 had multiple disease resistance (see table). □

Reaction of rice varieties to BS, BB, and ShR, Coimbatore, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a		
	BS	BB	ShR (% infection)
AS688	5	5	2
AS6520	3	3	10
AS18696	5	3	NT
AS18699	3	3	9
AS19103	3	3	2
AS19789	5	5	4
AS19903	5	3	NT
AS22954	3	5	NT
AS23598	5	3	15
AS23972	3	5	7

^a 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible; NT = not tested.

Reaction of IR varieties to rice yellow dwarf (RYD)

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Reactions of 26 IR varieties to RYD infection were tested in the greenhouse. Newly emerged *Nephotettix virescens* nymphs had 25-d acquisition access on RYD-infected TN1 plants. Six-day-old seedlings were confined with 2 viruliferous insects per seedling in test tubes for 1 d. Inoculated seedlings were transplanted in clay pots, kept in screened trays, and scored 40-60 d after inoculation. Percentage infection of IR varieties was 20-76%. TN1 was 97% infected. Six IR varieties had RYD infection lower than 30% and were considered resistant (see table). □

Reaction of ASD varieties to various rice diseases

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In 1983-84, 15 rice varieties released by the Paddy Experiment Station, Ambasamudram, were screened for disease resistance by artificial inoculation in the greenhouse at TNAU. Varieties were evaluated for resistance to brown spot (BS), bacterial blight (BB), sheath rot (ShR), blast (BI), and rice tungro virus (RTV) using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES). ASD5 and ASD11 had multiple disease resistance (see table). □

Disease resistance of ASD varieties, Coimbatore, India.^a

Variety	Disease rating ^a				
	BI	BS	BB	RTV	ShR
ASD1	3	5	5	5	5
ASD2	3	5	5	5	3
ASD3	3	5	7	5	3
ASD4	5	5	7	5	3
ASD5	3	3	3	1	3
ASD6	3	5	3	5	3
ASD7	5	3	5	5	3
ASD8	5	5	5	5	5
ASD9	5	3	5	3	3
ASD10	5	5	5	3	5
ASD11	3	3	3	3	3
ASD12	3	5	5	3	3
ASD13	NT	3	3	NT	NT
ASD14	7	3	5	3	5
ASD15	7	5	7	5	5

^a By the 1980 SES scale: 0-3 = resistant, 5 = moderate, 7 = susceptible, 9 = highly susceptible, NT = not tested.

IR varieties with low percentages of RYD infection, IIRRI, 1984.

Variety	Total tested ^a (no.)	Plants infected (%)
IR7	108	20
IR24	104	24
IR26	102	24
IR29	104	25
IR30	100	27
IR43	107	21
TN1 (check)	95	97

^a Based on 6 trials, each involving 20 seedlings/variety.

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

INSECT RESISTANCE

Behavior of two green leafhopper (GLH) colonies on three rice varieties

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We sought to determine if selection of a GLH *Nephotettix virescens* biotype on a variety with a major gene for resistance results in cross adaptation to another variety with the same major resistance gene.

The response of two GLH colonies—one from susceptible TN1 and selected on moderately resistant TAPL #796 for 18 generations, and another reared on TN1 for at least 100 generations—was determined based on survival, develop-